

www.arseam.com

DISASTER MANAGEMENT – AN OVERVIEW

Sunil Chaudhary

Steno

M.Com, MBA,

Faculty of commerce

Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Dayabagh, Agra, India

ABSTRACT

Disaster management is essentially a dynamic process. It comprises the classical management functions of planning, organizing, staffing, leading and controlling. It also involves many organizations, which must work together to prevent, mitigate, prepare for, respond to and recover from the effects of disaster. Disaster management would therefore include immediate response, recovery, prevention, mitigation, preparedness and the cycle goes on Humans have managed disasters and an overview of our past experiences shows that management of disasters is not a new concept. For example, in ancient India, droughts were effectively managed through conventional water conservation methods, which are still in use in certain parts of the country - like Rajasthan. Local communities have devised indigenous safety mechanisms and drought-oriented farming methods in many parts of the country.

Key Words: Prevent, preparedness, recovery, response

Introduction:

Organization and management of resources and responsibilities for dealing with all humanitarian aspects in emergencies is known as Disaster Management. It can be defined as the, in particular preparedness, response and recovery in order to lessen the impact of disasters. Disaster management aims to reduce or avoid the potential losses from hazards, assure prompt and appropriate assistance to victims of disaster, and achieve rapid and effective recovery. The Disaster management cycle illustrates the ongoing process by which governments, businesses, and civil society plan for and reduce the impact of disasters, react during and immediately following a disaster, and take steps to recover after a disaster has occurred. Appropriate actions at all points in the cycle lead to greater preparedness, better warnings, reduced vulnerability or the prevention of disasters during the next iteration of the cycle. The complete disaster

management cycle includes the shaping of public policies and plans that either modify the causes of disasters or mitigate their effects on people, property, and infrastructure.

The mitigation and preparedness phases occur as disaster management improvements are made in anticipation of a disaster event. Developmental considerations play a key role in contributing to the mitigation and preparation of a community to effectively confront a disaster. As a disaster occurs, disaster management actors, in particular humanitarian organizations become involved in the immediate response and long-term recovery phases. The four disaster management phases illustrated here not always, or even generally, occur in isolation or in this precise order. Often phases of the cycle overlap and the length of each phase greatly depends on the severity of the disaster.

Types of Disasters

There are two types of disasters

- (i) Natural Disasters: The disasters that are caused by nature are termed as natural disasters e.g., earthquake, cyclone etc.
- (ii) Man-made Disaster: The disasters which are caused as a result of human activities are termed as Man-Made Disasters e.g., Road accident, terrorist attack.

Natural Disasters:

1. Earthquake:

Earthquake is a sudden and violent shaking of ground causing great destruction as a result of movement of earth's crust. An earthquake has the potential to tsunami or volcanic eruption. Earthquake of magnitude 9.2 on the Richter's scale in 2004 in Indonesia is the second largest earthquake ever recorded. The deadliest earthquake happened in Central China, killing over 800,000 in 1556. People during that time and region lived in caves and died from the caves collapsing.

Earthquake mitigation strategies:

- a. Existing critical facilities built on reclaimed land should be inspected and retrofitted if necessary to ensure earthquake resistance.
- b. Future critical facilities should not be located on reclaimed land because of the high potential for liquefaction.
- c. Older unreinforced masonry buildings should be inspected and retrofitted if necessary to increase earthquake resistance.
- d. Older unreinforced masonry buildings should not be used for critical functions.

2. Cyclone: Cyclones (or more properly called Tropical Cyclones) are a type of severe spinning storm that occurs over the ocean near the tropics. The most famous Australian historic cyclone was Cyclone Tracy, December 1974, where around 11 people died in Darwin, Northern Territory. The direction they spin depends on which hemisphere they are in. In the Southern hemisphere they spin in a clockwise direction and Northern hemisphere they spin in an anti-clockwise direction.

Cyclone mitigation strategies:

- a. Future critical facilities should not be located in areas of accelerated winds.
- b. The most significant aspect of structural damage to buildings by high velocity wind results from roof damage. The roofs of existing buildings should be inspected and if necessary retrofitted to adequate standards.
- c. The roofs of existing critical facilities should be retrofitted to a higher standard to ensure wind resistance.
- d. Building openings such as windows and doors also suffer damage from high velocity winds. These openings if not constructed of wood or metal should be protected with shutters or temporary covers of adequate design.

3. Tsunami: Tsunamis are giant waves, initiated by a sudden change, usually in relative position of underwater tectonic plates. The sudden jerk is enough to propagate the wave; however, its power can be enhanced and fed by lunar positioning and boundaries that focus its energy.

Tsunami mitigation strategies:

- a. In some tsunami-prone countries earthquake engineering measures have been taken to reduce the damage caused onshore.
- b. Japan, where tsunami science and response measures first began following a disaster in 1896, has produced ever-more elaborate countermeasures and response plans. That country has built many tsunami walls of up to 4.5 meters (15 ft) to protect populated coastal areas.
- c. Other localities have built floodgates and channels to redirect the water from incoming tsunami.

4. Volcanic eruptions: Volcanic disasters are caused by lava flows, volcanic mudflows and pyroclastic flows triggered by volcanic activities such as eruptions. It covers extensive areas; volcanic disasters can cause a large-scale damages and serious personal injury. Secondary disasters such as debris flows are often triggered by rainfall after a volcanic eruption. In the 1815, the Indonesian eruption threw rocks more than 100 cubic km of ash killing 92,000 people. The greatest volcanic explosion occurred in Indonesia in 1883, which resulting in rocks hurling 55 km up into the air. The explosion was heard in Australia and generated a 40 m high tsunami, killing 36,000 people.

Volcanic disasters mitigation strategies:

- a. Learn about community warning systems and of disasters that can come from volcanoes (earthquakes, flooding, landslides, mudflows, thunderstorms, tsunamis)
- b. Make evacuation plans to higher ground with a backup route.
- c. Have disaster supplies on hand (flashlight, extra batteries, portable battery-operated radio, first aid kit, emergency food and water, nonelectric can opener, cash and credit cards, and sturdy shoes)

5. Floods: Flooding is the unusual presence of water on land to a depth which affects normal activities. Flooding can arise from: overflowing rivers (river flooding), heavy rainfall over a short duration (flash floods), or an unusual inflow of sea water onto land (ocean flooding). Ocean

flooding can be caused by storms such as hurricanes (storm surge), high tides (tidal flooding), seismic events (tsunami) or large landslides.

Flood mitigation strategies:

- a. Watercourses which pass through significant settlement areas should be properly configured and lined with concrete.
- b. Existing bridges should be inspected to determine which ones are too low or which have support pillars within the watercourse channel. Where possible these should be replaced as these features restrict water flow and cause the channels to be easily blocked with debris.
- c. Future bridges should not be built with these undesirable features.
- d. Buildings constructed adjacent to watercourses should be elevated by at least one meter to prevent potential flood inundation.
- e. Critical facilities should not be located adjacent to watercourses.

PRE-DISASTER PREVENTIVE MEASURES

Long-term measures

- Re-framing buildings' codes, guidelines, manuals and byelaws and their strict implementation. Tougher legislation for highly seismic areas.
- Incorporating earthquake resistant features in all buildings at high-risk areas.
- Making all public utilities like water supply systems, communication networks, electricity lines etc. earthquake-proof. Creating alternative arrangements to reduce damages to infrastructure facilities.
- Constructing earthquake-resistant community buildings and buildings (used to gather large groups during or after an earthquake) like schools, dharamshalas, hospitals, prayer halls, etc., especially in seismic zones of moderate to higher intensities.
- Supporting R&D in various aspects of disaster mitigation, preparedness and prevention and post-disaster management.
- Evolving educational curricula in architecture and engineering institutions and technical training in polytechnics and schools to include disaster related topics.

Medium term measures

- Retrofitting of weak structures in highly seismic zones.
- Preparation of disaster related literature in local languages with dos and don'ts for construction.
- Getting communities involved in the process of disaster mitigation through education and awareness.
- Networking of local NGOs working in the area of disaster management.

General Precautions

SUGGESTED ACTIONS

1. Develop a household disaster plan - have a household meeting to discuss what members would do and how they would communicate in the event of an incident.
2. Assemble a disaster supply kit with food, water, and first aid supplies at home, at work, and for your car.
3. Be sure to have a battery operated radio and extra batteries to stay informed.
4. Have a list of emergency contact numbers, including fire, police, and hospitals, near the phone.
5. Review and practice evacuation plans.
6. Learn about community sheltering resources and how to "shelter in place".
7. Check with school officials to determine their plans for emergency procedures.
8. Apartment residents should discuss emergency procedures with building managers.
9. Contact neighbors to discuss their plans and needs and how you can help each other.
10. If you have special needs, be sure to discuss your plans with family, friends, and your employers.
11. Be observant of any suspicious activity and report it to authorities.

12. Avoid high profile or symbolic locations.
13. Exercise caution when traveling.
14. Be sure to listen to what local authorities tell you about the situation in your area.

REFERENCES:

- Aguirre, B. E & Quarantelli, E. H. (2008). "Phenomenology of Death Counts in Disasters: the invisible dead in the 9/11 WTC attack". *International Journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*. Vol. 26 (1): 19–39.
- Alexander, David. *Principles of Emergency planning and Management*, Oxford University Press, 1 edition 2002, ISBN 978-0195218381
- Bankoff, Greg, Georg Frerks, Dorothea Hilhorst. *Mapping Vulnerability: Disasters, Development and People*, Routledge, 2004, ISBN 978-1853839641
- Barton, Allen H. *Communities in Disaster: A Sociological Analysis of Collective Stress Situations*, Doubleday, 1st edition 1969, ASIN: B0006BVVOW
- Beck, U. (2006). *Risk Society, towards a new modernity*. Buenos Aires, Paidós
- Hirshleifer, Jack (2008). "Disaster and Recovery". In David R. Henderson (ed.). *Concise Encyclopedia of Economics* (2nd ed.). Indianapolis: Library of Economics and Liberty
- Kahneman, D. y Tversky, A. (2004). "Choices, Values and frames". *American Psychologist*
- Korstanje, M. (2011). "The Scientific Sensationalism: short commentaries along with scientific risk perception". *E Journalist*.
- Korstanje, Maximiliano E. "Swine Flu in Buenos Aires: Beyond the Principle of Resilience", *International Journal of Disaster Resilience in the Built Environment*.
- Mileti, D. and Fitzpatrick, C. (2012). "The causal sequence of Risk communication in the Parkfield Earthquake Prediction experiment". *Risk Analysis*.
- Paul, B. K et al. (2012). "Public Response to Tornado Warnings: a comparative Study Tornadoes in Kansas, Missouri and Tennessee". *Quick Response Research Report*, no 165, Natural Hazard Center, Universidad of Colorado
- Phillips, B. D. (2015). "Disaster as a Discipline: The Status of Emergency Management Education in the US". *International Journal of Mass-Emergencies and Disasters*.
- Quarantelli, E. L. (2008). "Conventional Beliefs and Counterintuitive Realities". *Conventional Beliefs and Counterintuitive Realities in Social Research: an international Quarterly of the social Sciences*, Vol. 75 (3): 873–904.
- Scheper-Hughes, N. (2005). "Katrina: the disaster and its doubles". *Anthropology Today*. Vol. 21 (6).

Susanna M. Hoffman, Susanna M. & Anthony Oliver-Smith, authors & editors. Catastrophe and Culture: The Anthropology of Disaster, School of American Research Press, 1st edition 2002, ISBN 978-1930618152

Uscher-Pines, L. (2009). "Health effects of Relocation following disasters: a systematic review of literature". Disasters. Vol. 33 (1): 1–22.

Wilson, H. (2010). "Divine Sovereignty and The Global Climate Change debate". Essays in Philosophy. Vol. 11 (1): 1–7